

Formulation, Development, Estimation, and Evaluation of Serum using Cabbage Extract

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Abstract

Exposure to sun and other environmental factors can lead to skin damage, which in turn causes skin aging and wrinkles on the face. To combat these negative effects, it is important to take care of skin by using products that contain beneficial ingredients. One such product is serum. Serum is formulated to deliver active ingredients to the skin more efficiently than other skincare products. Vitamin C is a vital ingredient in serum that offers numerous benefits for the skin. It helps to brighten the skin, improve its texture, and reduce the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles. Oregano oil is another essential ingredient in serums that provides numerous benefits like antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, etc. By combining all the beneficial benefits of these ingredients a serum was formulated. Also, various tests were carried out to estimate the vitamin C content and various evaluation parameters of serum ensuring that the product is of high quality and effective.

Keywords: Vitamin C, Ascorbic acid, Cabbage, Oregano oil, Serum, Face, Skin.

1. Introduction

Serum, a staple in cosmetology, is an essential skincare product designed to deeply penetrate the skin with its lightweight gel or lotion formula, delivering active ingredients effectively. A quality serum can enhance skin firmness, and texture, minimize pore size, and boost moisture